

On the pileipellis of marine *Candolleomyces*

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Text

With collections from more and more *Candolleomyces* species studied by either myself or my colleagues, I have started to struggle with an idea getting stronger and stronger day by day—that other *Candolleomyces* species normally exhibit a pileipellis predominately composed of inflated cells (Figure 1) but why my new species with my colleagues *C. brunneovagabundus* and *C. albovagabundus* have (nearly) a cutis by filamentous hyphae in major (Yang *et al.* 2023)? Again and again I told myself to remember the hard days I stayed with these two marine babies on microscopes from dawn to dusk in which my observations were repeatedly confirmed by myself so that they should be reliable and accurate as seen, but, this has not successfully stopped that disgusting idea exploding today so I must re-examine my collections to make me feel better.

Very quickly, grabbing two collections most recently (3rd October 2024) earned from Xiwan Mangrove Park, one of *C. brunneovagabundus* (K24086, HTBM2101) and one of *C. albovagabundus* (K24087, HTBM2102), I made the pileus sections (and wrote this sheet). Before telling the results I have a new discovery eager to introduce, that I just noticed the “squamules” on pileus of HTBM2101, *C. brunneovagabundus*, are so similar to the veil remnants of non-sequestrate territorial *Candolleomyces* in texture (Figure 2, a line drawing from the pileus section of a species of *C. candolleanus* complex (L23376, HTBM1357) also attached here)! Now I think it’s likely that the “pileus squamules” of these marine *Candolleomyces* (including *C. albovagabundus* considering its close relationship to *C. brunneovagabundus*) are actually also veil remnants, if further, also approved by ontogenetic studies. However, all collections I observed earlier (of course including all those used for the proposal publication (Yang *et al.* 2023) of the two new species) do not have a similarity strong enough like this to make me consider their “squamules” as veils (Figure 3), as they look more homogeneous with the exposing tissues (plects) beneath and frequently are tightly retained on pileus. Possibly these “veil remnants” (if they are) have strong phenotypic plasticity given by seawater flushing during submerged times following tidal cycles or some other factors.

▲ **Figure 1.** A collection of a species in *Candolleomyces candolleanus* complex (L24184, HTBM2169) previously observed, photographed and illustrated by Jia Y. Lin. Note its pileipellis composed of inflated cells, which is typical for the genus *Candolleomyces*.

▲ **Figure 2.** Three observed collections, including one of *Candolleomyces brunneovagabundus* (K24086, HTBM2101), one of *C. albovagabundus* (K24087,

HTBM2102), and one of *C. candolleanus* complex (L23376, HTBM1357). (a) Collection site of HTBM2101. (b) Collection site of HTBM2102. (c) Intactly preserved basidiomata from HTBM2101 (left) and HTBM2102 (right), note the “squamules” on pileus of HTBM2101 similar to veil remnants of HTBM1357 (d). (d) A basidioma of HTBM1357 in situ. (e) Line drawing of the longitudinal and radial section of the pileus with veil remnants in (d). (f) Longitudinal section of HTBM2101. (g) Longitudinal section of HTBM2102. Photos and line drawing basically by Kun L. Yang, and Jia Y. Lin added encrusted dots for the line drawing of veil remnants in (e).

▲ **Figure 3.** Some representative photos of my earlier collections. The “squamules” on pileus of these collections did not remind me of veils in previous work. The bottom row shows *Candolleomyces albovagabundus*, and others are *C. brunneovagabundus*.

And here shows the results, there are many hyphal cells more or less inflated but still arranged in a manner of cutis in general (Figure 4, no staining applied, to present naturally pigmented cells), just like those described and illustrated in Yang *et al.* (2023). Of course they confirmed my previously observations again and I breathed a sigh of relief. I again went back to lament this bad habit of mine that I often try to overthrow my previous ideas but frequently after a hard attempt I will find that I was originally right. This is the second funny thing today after getting back my poor water bottle dropped into track area by my girlfriend from staffs of Guangzhou Metro.

It is impossible for me to infer the “natural” (or say, original) structure of the “pileus squamules” based on the existing materials, because there are too many impurities inside it possibly from seawater that have modified its original structure and blurred more details (the status in Figure 2c, the only one reminding me of veils, represents the one closest to natural structure ever known for these two species, I think).

▲ **Figure 4.** Light microscopy of longitudinal and radial pileus section of HTBM2101 (*Candolleomyces brunneovagabundus*) and HTBM2102 (*C. albovagabundus*). Sorry for the vague sight due to too many impurities like dirt on pileus but the general arrangement of hyphae can be recognized. Some thinner hyphae on surface are possibly from “veil remnants” but can not be confirmed at the current stage, based on these dried and dirty materials.

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References

Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M. & Yang, Z.L. 2023. Mushrooms adapted to seawater: two new species of *Candolleomyces* (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) from China. *Journal of Fungi* 9(12): 1204.